

DESIGNING STRATEGY MAPS FOR PRIVATE ENGINEERING COLLEGE

Nanang Alamsyah¹, Larisang² and Muhammad Ansyar Bora³

^{1,2,3}Department of Industrial Engineering, Sekolah Tinggi Teknik IbnuSinaBatam, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to design a strategic map for a private engineering college using the balanced scorecard method. There are two objectives: Key Performance Indicator (KPI) identification and KPI weighting. CIPP model is used to complete this study with the input of the study in the form of corporate statement and institutional strategy. Interview method used to determine KPI then continued by filling Analytic Hierarchy Process questionnaire in weighting KPI. There are 22 KPIs selected with distribution: three KPIs in financial perspective with 3.87% weighted value; five KPIs in the perspective of the customer with 47.86% weighted value; 6 KPIs from the perspective of Internal Business Process with 29.46% weighted value; and 8 KPIs from Learning & Growth perspective with 18.8% weighted value. The results of this strategic map design can be used in communicating all strategies implemented by the institution to all stakeholders and as a validation tool in strategy formulation.

Keywords: Strategic Management, Balanced Scorecard, Strategy Map, Analytic Hierarchy Process, Private Engineering College

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1992 an article published by Harvard business review as The Balanced Scorecard - Measure that drive performance[1]. This article explains that for an organization to measure the performance of the organization not only uses the financial aspect, but with other aspects that affect the organization as a whole. Previously before 1990 according to the book many organizations that take into account the performance of an organization still using the traditional system that is only by prioritizing the financial aspects, if the organization has more benefits than last year's profit means the organization including success. The drawback of the traditional method is the organizations only a short-term benefit for the finance aspect that has a major role is the top management. All decision making seeks to maximize profits so as to ignore other employee roles, such as a lack of initiative to decrease employee performance, and a lack of investment to employees so that employees can not have the necessary training to do the work that will affect the organization. To overcome this deficiency, then formed a new method that covers all aspects contained within an organization to measure the performance of the organization and can achieve the vision of the organization. Balanced Scorecard method formulated four aspects that have an important impact in the organization, namely: financial aspects, aspects of the customer, internal business aspects, aspects of learning and growth. By formulating these four aspects, an organization can achieve the desired vision.

In the balanced scorecard method there is a stage

called the strategy map. Definition of a strategy map is a visual presentation of the critical success factors of an organization and have a causal relationship[2]. Strategy Map depicts the diagram of four interrelated aspects, starting from the aspects of learning and growth, internal business aspects, customer aspects, financial aspects, so as to achieve the vision of the organization. Many organizational management use a strategic map because the strategy map allows users to read their vision and mission by drawing important roles from each aspect and detailing the work that each department of the organization should do.

In this study, the author will use the balanced scorecard method to formulate a strategy map that can help the management to achieve the desired vision. The object of study is STT IbnuSinaBatam. STT IbnuSinaBatam is located in BatamLubuk Baja Teuku Umar, STT Ibnu Sina managed by Educational Foundation of Ibnu SinaBatam. STT Ibnu Sina was established on 28th September 2001. The study was undertaken because of the lack of knowledge of students about the vision, mission and strategy of STT IbnuSinaBatam. By using the balanced scorecard method, the author can formulate the vision and mission STT Ibnu Sina in the form of diagrams that are easily understood and practiced to achieve a predetermined vision. In the diagram containing the position of STT Ibnu Sina, its objectives, and how to reach those goals.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Strategy Maps Definition

The strategy map presents a reciprocal relationship between performance measures and strategy variables. The strategy map is a visual presentation of the critical success factors of an organization and has a causal relationship. The strategy map provides a consistent way to present the strategy, so objectives and measurements can be generated and executed [3]. According to Neely and Bourne, the strategic map is a causality diagram derived from the company's strategy. Marr states the strategic map as a presentation that describes how an organization sees the organization itself [4].

From all the statements that have been quoted from the books on the strategic map, we can formulate that the strategic map is a diagram of an organization that has elements that have reciprocal relationships and have the end result to direct the organization toward the vision of the mission through a strategy that has been formulated.

In the book *Using Strategy Map to Drive Performance* there are 6 steps in strategy map making [5].

Step 1: Define the Primary Objective. In the next few years, what does it take to succeed? The first step is crucial, because it connects the strategy map to the initial step in creating and confirming a mission / value / vision of the organization. This step should differentiate what the organization understands for its main objectives and the strategies it wants to implement. A lot of confusion in this point. Many missions and visions are often considered to be fulfilled with satisfied customers, perfect service, best in their field. It is a critical and highly desirable outcome of all organizations. However, for organizations that want financial gain, the main objective should be economic. The main objective must be the first element in the strategy map. It must contain a financial target and time to reach it. The main objective example: Raise profit 6% in 3 years; Raise profit margins from 8% to 12%.

Step 2: Determine the desired value added. Companies that try to do everything will fail. Companies that provide unique value to selected customers can win prizes by becoming leaders in market share. To lead market share, companies must first differentiate market share in new and unusual ways, for example, what customer's value from a product or service? With this information, companies can focus on providing new value better than competitors. The second step in the strategy map is to determine the value that will help the organization in its market share. The three added values determined by Treacy and Wiersema provide perfect information in today's market share are: Good operation; Leader in the product; & Close to customers.

Step 3: select a financial strategy. After creating added value, organizations must create plans and strategies in earnings and costs. Financial strategies can be categorized in three important areas: Revenue

growth; Productivity; & Use of assets. All organizations should give attention in each of these categories. Knowledge in value-added can help the organization to know which of the three categories can be dominated by financial strategy. Organizations seeking operational efficiency will focus on reaching their key objectives through productivity and asset usage strategies. Organizations that seek closeness to customers or product leaders will put a smaller focus on this efficiency strategy, rather than trying to supplement income through a unique product.

Step 4: select the customer strategy. After creating a financial strategy, the organization must make plans and strategies to win market share. In other words, the organization must create and formulate customer strategies clearly. Customer strategy can be categorized in three important areas: Keeping and adding customers; Increase the profitability of each customer; & reduce the cost of each customer. Organizations should pay attention to each of these strategies. However, the choice of added value once again dictates where the organization should focus its activities and efforts. Organizations looking for good operations will use competitive rates to keep and add to customers, plus by increasing the profitability of each customer. Rigorous process and supply chain management will help in reducing the cost of each customer. The product leader will offer cutting-edge technology including services to increase customer volume and profitability of each customer. To keep and add customers, organizations seeking customer closeness will use strategies such as promotions and loyalty programs. By offering the perfect solution and package, the company is trying to increase the profitability of each customer. Like a product leader, a strategic plan should balance expenses and benefits.

Step 5: Implement through an internal perspective strategy. After making financial and customer strategies, organizations must take important action that can realize strategies to win market share. Internal perspective is how to choose and implement the right business processes to achieve customer strategy and financial trust organizations can generate the creation of the main objective. This perspective covers: Good internal international; Innovation and Leader in market share; & Leader in customer face.

Step 6: Plan your learning and growth strategies. After creating financial and customer strategies, and creating a workable plan. Organizations will be aware of the deficiencies in the knowledge, skills and abilities required to execute the chosen strategy. In the final step of this strategy map, the company develops the right strategy in learning and growth. The learning and growth perspective is about identifying deficiencies that can limit an organization's ability to carry out important processes that have been identified in an internal

perspective. Learning and growth can be classified into three main areas:HR (Human Resources); Information; &Organization.

2.2 Strategy Map Function

The function of the strategy map is:

- Clarify the course of the organization from non-financial success factors to financial results.
- Clarify the organization's strategy to its employees by showing how their duties relate to all of the organization's final goals.
- Can be used to connect business units and focus in the management process
- Complete the missing link of strategy formulation and strategy execution
- Tools to support performance measurement in an organization by highlighting important things in an organization.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study will go through three stages:

- Identifying the vision, mission, values, culture, and corporate strategy. Before drawing up the Balanced Scorecard, first the identification of the vision, mission, values, culture, and corporate strategy. It is first necessary to analyze the company's current situation and study the factors involved. Based on this analysis, then conducted an analysis of the company's strategy.
- Make a map of the strategy and to discuss the appropriate strategy objectives. This strategy map will illustrate the causal diagram of the relationship between the perspectives of the Balanced Scorecard. Then from the data and map of existing strategies, the goals will be discussed.
- Weighting all Perspectives and KPIs. To know the priority scale of each perspective and kpi, the researchers used AHP method

4. DATA COLLECTION & ANALYSIS

All data taken from the official document STT Ibnu Sina with permission of the highest leadership STT Ibn Sina[6].

Figure 1. Structure of STT Ibnu Sina

4.2 Corporate Statement

4.2.1. Vision

In the Year 2019 became a national superior engineering school, a global competitiveness based on faith and taqwa

4.2.2 Mission

- Organizing and developing the national standard quality education system in the field of engineering and relevant to the global development based on the values of faith and devotion.
- Develop scientific engineering through research activities of national quality and global perspective.
- Organizing and improving Community service activities in the field of technology that can provide solutions to problems faced by society, industry and government.

4.3 Strategic Statement

4.3.1. Objectives and Goals

- First objective: To produce graduates who are superior, virtuous, noble and globally competitive in engineering. Goals:
 - Excellent graduates
 - Graduates are virtuous and have noble character
 - Global competitive in engineering
- Second objective: Produce empirical, conceptual and technological knowledge for the benefit of scientific development through research results. Goals:
 - Increased number of research faculty and students
 - Improving the quality and relevance of lecturers' research
- Third objective: Increase the knowledge and skills of the community from the results of counseling, training and community development in the field of technology. The goal
 - Increasing the amount of community service performed by lecturers and students
 - Increased community knowledge and skills

4.3.2 Strategy

- Strategies for First Goals & Objectives a:
 - Advanced Study of Lecturers (S3)
 - Certification of Permanent Lecturer
 - Pekerti and AA training for permanent lecturers
 - Training Development of learning methods

- Training of Preparation of Learning materials / modules
 - Training / English courses for permanent lecturers
 - Recruitment of Permanent Lecturers
 - Upgrading of Lecturer's Lecturer to Students
 - Increased Anime prospective new students
 - Selection process is tightened
 - Facilitating students in academic activities
 - Facilitating students in non-academic activities (arts and sports)
 - Establish teaching load of lecturers in the field of science
 - Coordinate lecture materials between parallel lecturers or lecturers team (team teaching)
 - Develop e_learning learning support
 - Monitoring and evaluation of lectures
 - Assessment of lecturing process by students
 - Increasing the number of lecturers using English language teaching materials
 - Increase in the number of bilingual classes in the lecture
 - Improved learning methods
 - Improve GPA of graduates
 - Reduce Waiting period graduates get jobs
 - Include employees in education and training programs in accordance with their field of work
 - Increased work productivity
 - Increasing the number and capacity of facilities and infrastructure Teaching and learning process
 - Increasing the number of classroom and laboratory facilities
 - Increasing the number of PBM facilities
 - Computer: Classroom & Laboratory
 - LCD / Projector: Classroom, Seminar Room & Laboratory
 - Internet Connection
 - Developing academic and non academic information system application: Finance, Inventory, Student, Study Plan Card (KRS), Course Schedule, Course Value, Academic Transcript, Graduate, Lecturer and Staff, Library
- b. Strategies for Objectives 1 & Goals b:
- Applying the value of discipline, honesty and decency in the lecture process
 - No complaints regarding the morality and ethics of graduates in the graduate user feedback
 - Consultation and academic guidance also foster psychological and moral problems
 - 90% of students pass the religion and citizenship courses at least B
- c. Strategy for Objectives 1 & Objectives c:
- Evaluate and restructure the Competency-Based Curriculum by Incorporating the Core Curriculum according to the field of expertise of each study program
- Conduct evaluation of GBPP, syllabus, lecture contract, RPKPS, module and teaching materials
 - Improving the quality and quantity as well as evaluating the module / teaching materials
 - Collect feedback from graduates and graduate users about the curriculum
 - Benchmarking with other universities that have the same study program
 - Improving the quality of the final project
 - Evaluate the Final Writing Handbook
 - Monitoring, evaluation, and follow-up mentoring
 - Accelerate the completion of the final project
 - Providing technical skill training courses according to each study program
 - Foreign language training / courses
 - 11. Test TOEFL / IELTS with minimum score of 450 / 5,5 to follow thesis trial
 - Require to follow scientific skill training of certified informatics technique as requirement of thesis trial
 - Image enhancement
 - Increasing the value of accreditation institutions and Prodi
 - Cooperate with various agencies
 - Internal quality assurance
- d. Strategies for Second Goals & Goals a:
- Each lecturer keeps conducting research at least 1 time per year
 - Require and facilitate lecturers to conduct research
 - Include lecturers in research seminars or workshops
 - Include students in research activities of lecturers
 - Conducting research seminars or workshops
 - Provide financing on research faculty and students
 - Improvement of lecturers research whose source of financing comes from outside the institution
 - Engage students in scientific activities / competitions
 - Conducting training in research methodology and data analysis
 - Rewrite the study manual
- e. Strategies for Objectives 2 & Objectives b:
- Produce empirical, conceptual and technological research
 - Registering intellectual property research
 - Development of teaching materials based on research results
 - Require to publish the results of research of permanent lecturers
 - Making an online online journal

- Publishing an online journal
- f. Strategies for Objectives 3 & Goals a:
 - Require and facilitate lecturers to conduct PKM
 - 2.PKM is directed to the utilization of information technology work
 - Improvement of external financing of PKM
 - Provide PKM financing for lecturers and students
 - Include lecturers in PKM training / workshop activities
 - Involving students in PKM activities
- g. Strategies for Objectives 3 & Objectives b:
 - Extension-counseling to the community on

the field of technology

- Conduct training on the use of information technology
- Coaching to the community (Village and SMEs) in the field of information technology

After all the data has been collected, the researcher tries to categorize the existing strategy according to the 4 balanced scorecard perspectives. But for the financial perspective, it was not found an adequate strategy. Furthermore, the researcher tried to confirm to the management of STT Ibnu Sina to ascertain whether there is a strategy applied but not listed in the document. And it is true, there are strategies related to the financial perspective that has

Figure 2. Strategy Maps of STT Ibnu Sina

been run but not listed in the document. At this stage, researchers believe that strategit map formation can validate the strategies implemented by the institution. Furthermore, the strategy map that has been formulated, can be seen in Figure 2.

4.3.3 Strategy Map Weighting

a. Determination of Weight Perspective

The weighting of the questionnaires was done by the head of STT IbnuSinaBatam. Balanced Scorecard as a performance measurement, there are four perspectives to consider, namely:

- F: Financial perspective
 - C: Customer perspective
 - I: Internal business process perspective, and
 - G: Perspective of growth and learning
- Comparison of the level of importance / influence relative between one perspectives with another perspective.

Table1 Comparison of Alternative Perspectives

Alternative	F	C	I	G
F	1	1/9	1/8	1/7
C	9	1	2	3
I	8	1/2	1	2
G	7	1/3	1/2	1
CI		0.031		
CR		0.03		

Table2 Weight Perspective

Perspective	F	C	I	G
Weight	3.87%	47.86%	29.46%	18.8%

b. Determination Weight Initiative Strategy

1. Perspective finance

In perspective finance there three priority initiative strategy companythat need considered, namely:

- F1: Operational Fund
- F2 : Research Funding
- F3 : Dana PKM

Comparison based on level interests / influence relatively between oneinitiative strategies with more.

Table 3 Comparison of Financial Perspective

Alternative	F1	F2	F3
F1	1	1	1
F2	1	1	1
F3	1	1	1
CI		0	
CR		0	

Table4 Financial Weights

Financial	F1	F2	F3
Weight	33.33%	33.33%	33.33%

2. Perspective customer

In perspective customer there two initiative strategy companyneed considered, namely:

- C1: Work on Multinational Corporations
- C2: Enhancement Quality College student
- C3: Doing Activities Counseling, Training and Coaching Society
- C4: No do things contrary with ethics and moral
- C5: No there is complaint the moral and ethics graduates in bait behind users graduates

Comparison based on level interests / influence relatively between one initiativestrategy with others

Table5 Comparison of Customer Perspective

Alternative	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	1	1/7	1/6	1/8	1/8
C2	7	1	2	1/2	1/2
C3	6	0.5	1	1/3	1/3
C4	8	2	3	1	1
C5	8	2	3	1	1
CI			0.025		
CR			0.2		

Table6 Weights Perspective Customer

Customer	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Weight	3.23%	19.34%	12.46%	32.49%	32.49%

3. Internal business process perspective

In there are internal business process perspective three initiative strategy companies that need to be considered, namely:

- I1: Increased Quality Task End
- I2: Lift
- I3: Increase Quality System information Academic and non-academic courses
- I4: Meningkatkan the quality of the learning process teach
- I5: Increased amount and capacity means and infrastructure and learning process teach
- I6: Curriculum based competencies that equip the hard skills (science and technology) and soft skills

Comparison based on level interests / influence relatively between oneinitiative strategies with more.

Table7 Comparison Internal Business Process Perspective

Alternative	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6
I1	1	1/8	1/9	1/9	1/7	1/8
I2	8	1	1/2	1/2	2	1
I3	9	2	1	1	3	2
I4	9	2	1	1	3	2
I5	7	1/2	1/3	1/3	1	1/2
I6	8	1	1/2	1/2	2	1
CI	0.054					
CR	0.04					

Table8 Weights Internal Business Processes

Internal Business Process	Weight
I1	2.31%
I2	16.04%
I3	27.8%
I4	27.8%
I5	10.02%
I6	16.04%

4. Perspective growth and learning

In perspective growth and learning there three initiatives strategy Companies that need to be considered, namely:

- G1: Increase quality lecturer
- G2: Enhancement quality service (professionalism employee / labor education)
- G3: Produce Empirical research, conceptual and creation technology
- G4: Publish results research lecturer permanent
- G5: College student involved in research lecturer
- G6: Every lecturer permanent doing devotion to community at least 1 time per year
- G7: Every lecturer permanent doing study at least 1 time per year
- G8: Engaging college student in devotion to community lecturer

Compare based on level interests / influence relatively between one initiative strategy with more.

Table9 Comparison Perspective Learning & Growth

Alternative	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6	G7	G8
G1	1	1/8	1/8	1/7	1/7	1/7	1/8	1/8
G2	8	1	1	2	2	2	1	1
G3	8	1	1	2	2	2	1	1
G4	7	1/2	1/2	1	1	1	1/2	1/2
G5	7	1/2	1/2	1	1	1	1/2	1/2

G6	7	1/2	1/2	1	1	1	1/2	1/2
G7	8	1	1	2	2	2	1	1
G8	8	1	1	2	2	2	1	1
CI	0.209							
CR	0.15							

Table10 Weight Learning and Growth

Learning & Growth	Weight
G1	1.82%
G2	17.47%
G3	17.47%
G4	9.43%
G5	9.43%
G6	9.43%
G7	17.47%
G8	17.47%

Table 11 Weight All Perspectives & KPIs

Perspective KPI	Finance	Customer	Internal Business Process	Learning & Growth
	3.87%	47.86%	29.46%	18.80%
1	1.29%	1.54%	0.68%	0.34%
2	1.29%	9.25%	4.73%	3.29%
3	1.29%	5.96%	8.19%	3.29%
4		15.55%	8.19%	1.77%
5		15.55%	2.95%	1.77%
6			4.73%	1.77%
7				3.29%
8				3.29%

5. CONCLUSION

We have created strategic map with total number of KPI 32, with division: financial perspective of 3 KPI; Customer perspective 5 KPIs; Internal business process perspective of 6 KPIs; and 8 learning and growth perspective of KPI.

The weighting of all perspectives and KPIs has been calculated with the results:

No	Perspective / KPI	Weight
F	Financial Perspective	3.87%
F1	Operational Fund	1.29%
F2	Research funding	1.29%
F3	PKM Fund	1.29%
C	Customer Perspective	47.86%
C1	Working on Multinational Enterprises	1.54%
C2	Improved Student Quality	9.25%

C3	Conducting Extension Activities, Training and Community Development	5.96%
C4	Not Doing things that are against ethics and morals	15.55%
C5	No complaints about the morale and ethics of graduates in the graduate user feedback	15.55%
I.	Internal Business Process Perspective	29.46%
I1	Improving the Quality of Final Project	0.68%
I2	Image Improvement with a weight of	4.73%
I3	Improve the Quality of Academic Information System and non academic program of study	8.19%
I4	Improving the quality of teaching and learning process	8.19%
I5	Increasing the number and capacity of facilities and infrastructure of teaching and learning process	2.95%
I6	Competency-based curriculum that equips hard skills (science and technology) and soft skills	4.73%
G	Learning and growth perspective	18.8%
G1	Improve the quality of lecturers	0.34%
G2	Improved quality of service (professionalism of employees / education personnel)	3.29%
G3	Produce empirical, conceptual and technological research	3.29%
G4	Publish the results of research of permanent lecturers	1.77%
G5	Students are involved in lecturer's research	1.77%
G6	Each lecturer still performs dedication to the community at least 1 time per year	1.77%
G7	Each lecturer still conducting research at least 1 time per year	3.29%

G8	Involve students in devotion to the lecturers community	3.29%
----	---	-------

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank LPPM STT IbnuSina who has facilitated us in funding this research. In addition, we also thank the management of STT IbnuSina who was willing to "dissect" all corporate statement & strategy statement. Hopefully this can be useful concretely.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] R. S. Kaplan and D. P. Norton, "The Balanced Scorecard - Measures that Drives Performance," *Harvard Business Review Reprint*, pp. 71-79, 1992.
- [2] R. S. Kaplan and D. P. Norton, "Conceptual Foundation of Balanced Scorecard," *Harvard Business School*, pp. 10-74, 2010.
- [3] R. S. Kaplan and D. P. Norton, *The Balanced Scorecard: Translating Strategy into action*, Boston Massachusetts: Harvard Business School Press, 1996.
- [4] A. Neely and M. Bourne, "Why Measurement Initiatives Fail," *Measuring Business Excellence*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 3-7, 2000.
- [5] K. W. Witt, *Using Strategy Maps to Drive Performance*, 2004.
- [6] STT Ibnu Sina Batam, *SK No. 027/STT/YAPISTA/II/2014 tentang Penetapan Visi, Misi, Tujuan STT Ibnu Sina Batam Periode tahun 2014-2019*, Batam: STT Ibnu Sina Batam, 2014.